

THE EFFECTS OF COST AND WEIGHT EFFICIENT STRUCTURAL DESIGN FOR MANUFACTURING OF COMPOSITE AUTOMOTIVE BODY STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The automotive industry stands in front of a technology shift in order to adapt to future legislations on more energy efficient cars. Carbon fibre composites are by many seen as the only solution to succeed with this quest. Composite design and manufacturing methodologies need to be developed in order to reach a cost and weight effective design for high annual volumes. Potential advantages with composite materials, such as enabling manufacturing of highly integrated structures with complex geometries, i.e. integral designs, must be explored and questioned. In high series volumes, differential designs, i.e. structures divided with the intention of reducing the part complexity, seems to become more competitive.

In this work the effect of financial and structural performance of differential and integral design solutions are addressed. Constraints on laminate and ply thickness as well as minimum ply cut area are considered and their impact on the weight optimisation evaluated. An automotive body structure section is studied and the weight and manufacturing cost is evaluated for both integral and differential design solutions. A cost model addressing both manufacturing and assembly processes are used together with finite element optimisation for the analysis. The results show that the weight efficiency for all design solutions is greatly reduced if the partitioning is made with of a clear focus. The results emphasise the importance of an efficient partitioning philosophy if the advantages of differential design are to be experienced to its fullest and to be able to create a manufacturing optimised design offering both cost and weight efficiency.

1 INTRODUCTION

The cost and weight efficiency of a composite automotive body structure is much by influenced by the global architecture, structural design, manufacturing process and expected annual volumes. Few would question that carbon fibre composites could reduce the structural weight of a body structure compared to a steel design. The potential weight reduction could be as high as 50-80%[1], however, it will come with a great increase in cost. The manufacturing of a structural optimised composite design is often a labour intensive and slow manufacturing process. In a low volume scenario, the cost drivers are investments in tools and high labour cost[2]. Therefore, carbon fibre composite structures for low volume products are mostly made in integral designs, taking advantage of the potential of producing highly complex and large structures in one tool[3]. In that way the investment cost can be minimised and the requirement of expensive assembly processes avoided.

Until recently, carbon fibre composites have been used in cost insensitive products where the focus has been on the reduction of weight and not on the part cost. However, with introduction of carbon fibre composites in the aerospace industry that trend was broken. The introduction was motivated by a

high financial appreciation for weight reduction and its benefits on the overall life cycle cost[4]. The value of weight is the key factor and in order to find a business case such value is required to be high, like in the aerospace industry where a value of weight is claimed to be at least 370€/kg[5]. The contradiction is seen in the automotive industry where the financial appreciation for weight reduction is low, around 0.3-6 €/kg[6], [7]. A much more cost efficient introduction carbon fibre composites must therefore be found.

The automotive industry also requires high manufacturing volumes which will change the cost breakdown and drivers of composite manufacturing as well as its potential advantages. Fuchs et al[8] describe the feedstock cost as the main cost drivers for a highly automated composite manufacturing aimed for high volumes. Hence, material utilization becomes an important factor when designing a cost effective structural part together with an overall ambition to reduce cycle times to limit the required investments. Furthermore, a relation was proposed in[9] for high volume composite manufacturing which said that geometric complexity drives scrap and therefore cost benefits could be found by dividing a composite structure. Consequently, the importance to strive for integral design and large integrations as suggested is the case in custom and low volume series would be reduced for higher volumes.

Material cost is not only governed by the scrap cost but of the weight of the final structure and therefore an optimised structural design might improve material cost. Partitioning can have great impact on the cost of a composite part in regard to optimised material utilisation, but the partitioning is also influencing the performance as seen in. The approach of how to split the composite structure therefore becomes crucial for both cost and performance of the structure. These properties are also intimately related, if the partitioning influence the performance in a negative way the overall weight increases and by that material cost. Therefore, the partitioning approach governs the cost and performance of the structure and a balance between a cost effective production and a structural optimised part must be sought.

This paper builds on the previous investigation of the cost and weight efficiency of integral and differential designs[9]. It was seen in[9] that minimising complexity can be beneficial for both performance and cost, however the joints were placed in highly stressed areas. This is contrary to the guidelines[10], [11] on how to position split lines in composite structures, which do recommend a more conservative approach which strives for the joint never to become the weakest link. This approach results in a limited weight increase since additional material required for the joint is small however the joint position is restricted in its benefits on complexity reduction and improved stiffness for the structure. The method used for investigating these approaches is considered also in this work. A case study is conducted to seek if an improved cost and weight balance can be found by adapting a mixed partitioning philosophy between the two approaches investigated in[12]. The aim is to define a cost and weight effective design for composite structures. A multi objective analysis of the implementation of different partitioning philosophies was analysed. Herein the effects on cost and weight is analysed by following the cost partition analysis and structural optimised designs.

2 METHOD

The cost and weight efficiency of a structure, integral or differential, is analysed by comparing the weight of an optimised structural design with the manufacturing cost of the same. The analysis follows the scheme shown in Fig. 1, and the evaluation step assesses the results. The partition analysis from[9] is considered to define the final number of parts based on the reduction of geometric complexity. A complexity factor, C , is used defined as:

$$C = A_c/A_p \quad (1)$$

where A_c is the complete surface area of the part and A_p the projected area of the part. The final number of suggested parts is defined by applying the partition analysis from[9] with the exception that each

partitioning is made in sequence and then analysed if a further partitioning of the structure should be made to improve the manufacturing cost. When no further cost benefits can be found the partitioning is ended. Dependent of where the split lines are placed the reduction of complexity will be more or less great and the final number of parts will vary. Therefore, the partitioning philosophy is greatly affecting both cost and structural performance of the structure. Thereafter, when the global architecture of the structure is finalised a FEM analysis is made to optimise the structural design for min weight. The final weight and cost of the solutions can then be compared.

Figure 1: Method scheme.

3 CASE STUDY

A case study is performed considering an area consisting of the front and rear floor together with the firewall of an automotive body structure, shown in Figure 2. The area is stiffness dimensioned and the overall geometric and complexity properties are given in Table 1.

Figure 2: initial geometric definition or structural area suitable for RTM process with epoxy carbon fibre material system.

	Requirements Torsional Stiffness [kNm/deg]	Projected area [m ²]	Complete area [m ²]	Complexity factor [9]
Floor structure	1.39	5.49	10.7	1,94

Table 1: Mechanical requirements, overall geometric and complexity properties

3.1 Material and Process

The manufacturing process considered in this study is Resin Transfer Moulding, RTM and the material system epoxy resin together with carbon fibre non-crimp fabric, NCF. An epoxy resin[13] suited for RTM and a standard high strength carbon fibre, Hexcel AS4[14] are used with material properties as described in Table 2.

Materials	Young's modulus (E1) [GPa]	Young's modulus (E2) [GPa]	Shear modulus [GPa]	Density [g/cm ³]	Poisson's ratio	Strain to failure
NCF CFRP[13], [14]	140	10	3	1,5	0.35	-
Epoxy adhesive[15]	1.8	-	-	1.25		11%

Table 2: material data

3.2 Finite element analysis

The optimisation routine of Altair Hyper Works; Optimisation routine for composite structure[16] is used for the finite element analysis and structural optimisation. The laminates are modelled with shell elements and the adhesive bond line is made by solid elements. Table 3 shows the design constraints considered for the optimisation and Table 2 shows the material data. Furthermore, the laminate design is idealized in the sense that no overlapping plies due to complicated draping are considered.

Design constraints	Data
Max laminate thickness	20 mm
Min laminate thickness	1 mm
Min ply thickness	0.1 mm
Number allowed plies per fibre orientation	16
Allowed fibre angles	0/90/45/-45
	Balanced layup
Adhesive thickness	1 mm

Table 3: Design constraints for optimisation routine

The load case for the torsional stiffness requirements in the case study are modelled as shown in Figure 3a.

Figure 3: Load case set-ups

3.3 Joining

Single overlap joint, as shown in Figure 4a, is considered in the FEM model as well as cost model. Moreover, for joining in close proximity to sharp angles single supported corner joint design is used[17], shown in Figure 4b. The cost model considers the same material addition and investments for both joints

Figure 4: a) single overlap joint, b) single overlap corner joint

3.4 Overlap length and joint design

The same overlap length is used for both the single supported corner joint and single overlap joint. The overlap length is often based on the relation between the laminate thickness and overlap length[18], [19]. The overlap length recommendations varies greatly Kelly et al[18] describes number between 8:1 for test samples to 80:1 for projects in the aerospace industry. In this paper 30:1 in relation to the laminate thickness is used according industry standards and a reasonable reduction compared to the aerospace industry, where 1:60 is suggested[14] for single lap joints. A balanced joint is designed, equal adherent thickness, to minimise peel loads and the bending moment at the joint ends[14]. The laminate in an optimised design will most likely vary in thickness over the length of the joint for all partition philosophies analysed herein. This must also be addressed in the overlap length design. Hart-smith¹⁴ describes an approach utilised in the project Primarily Adhesively Bonded Structure Technology (PABST) were a universal overlap length was considered only related to the thin laminate and locally thicker areas were only tapered to reduce eventual induced peel loads. This approach is adapted also in this case study and overlap length is considered for each joint based on the average laminate thickness in the structure. Allowed strain in the adhesive is set to 1/10 of strain to failure[10] according to aerospace guidelines. The surface ply orientation is considered optimal for the joint design not to experience any reduced strength because of surface effects[18].

3.5 Partition philosophies

An attempt to combine the two previously investigated partition philosophies[12] is addressed. Hence, the three philosophies considered in the case study are; positioning the joint in areas of minimum stress and strain as well as thin laminates, this partition philosophy is herein after referred to as **MinStress**; the approach for cost efficiency where the positioning of the joints are made to reduce complexity herein after referred to as **MinComp** and finally the attempt to define a more efficient portioning by combining the approached herein called **MinMix**.

3.6 Cost model

Figure 5, Cost model processes for RTM manufacturing and assembly cost.

The cost model outline is seen in Figure 5 and describes the automated RTM process steps and assembly process considered in the case study.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Design solution	Integral	MinStress	MinMix	MinComp
Number of parts [n]	1	5	5	4
Average part complexity index[9]	1,95	1,68	1,52	1,42
COST [€]	2281	1519	1549	1353
WEIGHT [kg]	57.8	61.2	62.5	53.7
COST DIF [€]	NA	= -732€	= 762€	= -928€
WEIGHT DIF [kg]	NA	= - 3.4kg	= - 4.7kg	= - 4.1kg

Table 4: Results of the cost and weight analysis of the different partition philosophies

The results are summarized and shown in Table 2. As seen in Figure 5, MinMix will consist of 5 pieces, as a result of with which efficiency the method reduces the complexity of the structure. This is a higher number of parts than MinComp which is purely focused on reducing the complexity. It is the same number of parts as the MinStress approach, though the average complexity of the remaining parts is lower considering the approach has greater focus on complexity. Therefore, the MinMix also should experience cost benefits based on improved material utilisation and manufacturing process compared to MinStress. But, as seen in previous work MinComp, an approach only focusing on reducing complexity, will consist of fewer parts with the lowest average part complexity. The reason is the rapid reduction of complexity in each partition.

MinMix has a higher average complexity than MinComp which indicates a more expensive manufacturing. Together with the highest structural weight the overall cost becomes the highest of all three differential design though still lower than the integral solution. The positioning of the joints is main reason behind these results, both the effect on geometric complexity as well as the structural performance. In the case of the MinMix the joints are neither position so to be the least subjected to stress i.e. a minimum of added weight due to thin laminates in the joint, nor place to reduce the complexity to the fullest. Also, the positioning in MinMix requires for some areas, thick laminates to address the strain in the joint adding weight but not stiffness in important areas as is the case with MinComp. Therefore, the additional material required for the structure only increases the overall cost.

Figure 6: a) MinStress

Figure 6: b) MinComp

Figure 6: c) MinMix

4 CONCLUSIONS

Manufacturing and design constraints as well as global architecture are all intensely important for the final cost and weight performance of a composite structure. It is seen that reducing the freedom of design i.e. maximum thickness, number of plies etc. some advantages with an integral design is lost. Differential designs are considering more variables of freedom in the structural design phase due to multiple parts e.g. more total number of plies to design the part. While it is claimed that a differential design can be both more cost as well as weight efficient compared to an integral design the results show clearly that the choice of partitioning philosophy is critical. The partition must be made with a clear motive to improve cost but also to exploit the additional material due to the joints. If succeeded, a differential design can bring both financial and technical benefits and the contrary if the objective is failed. Therefore, partitioning of composite structure has a great potential but needs to be well analyzed before introduced to not have the opposite effect.

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